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Updated assessment of developments and revision of scientific challenge - Enabling Next-Generation Plasma Accelerators for Real World Applications with PIConGPU

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we summarize our activities toward the scientific challenge of simulating compact laser-plasma accelerators in the Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) geometry for electron acceleration beyond 10 GeV energy.

We realized in our earlier work that PIConGPU’s capabilities of modeling the complex laser fields in TWEAC geometries were insufficient to accurately simulate the target test case. Therefore, we developed and implemented a new Traveling-wave Thomson-scattering (TWTS) laser model **TWTSTight** which significantly improved modeling accuracy. It is well tested and ready to be used in production runs.

Two further challenges were discovered when using the new laser model. First, the improved modeling comes at the cost of longer compute times. Second, we observed unforeseen numerical issues, specifically laser field reflections, were observed at the boundaries of the simulation box. The causes for these were identified and a mitigation strategy can be formulated, however, this is subject to experimentation and requires more time.

Our earlier investigations also found that our performance portability library alpaka, on top of which PIConGPU is built, cannot be well analyzed by compilers of the new EPI compute architectures, resulting in poor auto-vectorization. After analyzing the problem, we started the development of **alpaka3** now, implementing the idea of alpaka from scratch in a new development, in order to better express vector unit parallelism, aid auto-vectorization and increase usability. While first applications of our users were already ported to alpaka3, further development is necessary to port PIConGPU to the new library.

A solution to the challenge of the I/O bottleneck for simulation data write-out and analysis has been developed and successfully implemented in production. The solution utilizes data streaming directly from the producer to the consumer, i. e. a PIConGPU simulation and a Machine Learning application, respectively, via openPMD with ADIOS2. This allows us to circumvent the lack of adequate disk capacity and bandwidth by enabling data to reside in-memory and be distributed via network between the two applications running on different nodes of the compute cluster at the same time.

We have extended PIConGPU’s CI infrastructure to include runtime testing (both unit tests and integration tests). While we run unit tests automatically, integration tests, crucial for validating full physics workflows, are manually triggered, as they consume significant CI resources. Performing meaningful integration tests regularly, e. g. with every pull request or on a daily or weekly basis, is a very important but ultimately too big task for standard, shared CI resources. To address this, we request CASTIEL2’s support in accessing CI runners on EuroHPC systems, which would allow us to run large-scale integration tests automatically, ensuring readiness for deployment on EuroHPC systems and improving code reliability.

In summary, we are progressing steadily along the work plan, having resolved key challenges, while adapting it to address new, unforeseen issues.

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1 Revision of the Scientific Challenge

The initial report D1.3 defined the scientific challenges as follows.

1.1 Physics challenges

- Identify the most suitable Traveling-Wave Electron Acceleration (TWEAC) regimes for stable acceleration.
- Demonstrate acceleration of electrons in a single stage beyond 10 GeV with TWEAC.
- Assess which injection techniques of standard Laser-Plasma Accelerators (LPAs) can be employed for TWEAC.
- Evaluate possibilities for injection of high-brightness electrons.
- Explore new capabilities of TWEAC with respect to electron injection techniques.

As our scientific goal did not change, these challenges are up-to-date. The first revision D1.7 added

- Identify TWEAC regimes where the laser pulse can be modeled with existing methods

Since then, our physics-related work focused on improving the laser modeling capabilities of PIconGPU in order to accurately simulate small interaction angle regimes where we expect highest efficiency of laser to electron energy transfer. The newly implemented **TWTSTight** laser accurately models the vector fields of the laser pulse, taking weak laser components into account, see Pull Requests (PRs) #5231, #5273, #5274, #5305. Specifically small interaction angle regimes of TWEAC, where lasers are tightly focused and propagate over long distances, can be accurately simulated now. The item added in D1.7 is therefore achieved and cleared.

1.2 Computational resources and numerical challenges

The initial report D1.3 defined the numerical challenges as follows.

- Long-term stability: Simulations of TWEAC beyond 10 GeV will run on the order of 10^6 timesteps. Stability of the solvers, in terms of artificial amplification of noise or small errors, needs to be studied.
- Accuracy: If stability of the simulation setup is given, we want to ensure high-fidelity simulation results, i. e. keep errors due to numerical inaccuracies low. We will use higher order schemes for the solvers, i. e. field solver, particle pusher, and particle shape. These schemes are already implemented.
- Simulation volume size: Due to the line focus geometry, the laser pulses used in TWEAC have a large width in the plane transverse to the focal plane compared to the cylindrical symmetric laser pulses used in standard Laser-Wakefield Accelerators (LWFAs). In order to capture the plasma cavity formation correctly in the

Figure 1: Current challenges in the simulation model of TWEAC: (a) Distorted field due to field artifacts when inserting TWEAC lasers from the side without a temporal window plus field reflections due to gracing incidence of the laser on the Perfectly Matching Layer boundaries in small interaction angle scenarios; (b) expected field distribution from a reference implementation.

simulation, large plasma volumes have to be simulated. Together with the increased accuracy requirement, this increases the required computational resources by orders of magnitude compared to standard LWFA simulations.

As before, these challenges still exist and are being actively worked on.

The challenge ‘Laser model accuracy: implement and test a cylindrical quasi-Gaussian vector beam’, which was newly defined in D1.7 has been met with the new laser implementation.

However, while testing the improved laser model, we observed further challenges in other modeling aspects of the simulation, see fig. 1. These are currently being worked on:

- Directly inserting TWEAC lasers from the side without a temporal window generates initial field artifacts. A Blackman-Nuttall window (ref. [2]) will be implemented in order to enable a shallow field upramp.
- Settings of the Perfectly Matching Layers boundaries have to be optimized since there are significant reflections visible in small interaction angle scenarios where the laser almost co-propagates to the transverse boundaries.

2 Summary of Developments

2.1 PIConGPU software release and continued development

On 18th December 2024, a new release of PIConGPU was published on Github: <https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu>.

Highlights of this PIConGPU release are a new atomic physics model FLYonPIC 2.0, the shadowgraphy plugin as advanced synthetic diagnostic of laser plasma interactions, a

new laser profile `FromOpenPMDPulse` allowing to load electric fields in transverse space and time domain into the simulation via `incidentField`, enhanced OpenPMD functionality, and support for the RISC-V ecosystem.

In addition, between 1st December 2024 and 1st June 2025 112 Pull Requests, by 16 contributors in total, were merged into mainline PIConGPU. These add functionality, ease usage, extend documentation, and fix bugs.

2.2 Developing alpaka3

A substantial amount of work is currently being invested into a redesign and new implementation of our performance-portability layer alpaka, the new library being *alpaka3*, see <https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka3>. During the project lifetime, we found within the consortium that alpaka cannot fully utilize vector units of RISC-V, the upcoming European exascale compute architecture, due to failing auto-vectorization by the compiler, see e. g. deliverables D1.7 and D2.5. The new development of alpaka3 started in November 2024 and includes – among other things – a hardware-agnostic kernel language that can accurately express the various levels of parallelism found in modern computing hardware. As a first step, this will aid auto-vectorization. This is already starting to receive confirmation within the consortium, see deliverable D2.5. But it will also allow the backend to implement explicit parallelization strategies, including vectorization, to further tune performance. Future benchmarking and collaboration within the consortium will show if this could be beneficial beyond the auto-vectorization capabilities of modern compilers.

2.3 Utilizing the data streaming capability in PIConGPU via openPMD/ADIOS2 in production

The last roadmap, presented in deliverable 1.7, featured item ‘3.2 Extend and test streaming capability in PIConGPU using openPMD/ADIOS2 to be used in production’. This item represented the method to realize item ‘1.3. In-transit data analysis to tackle the data deluge’ of the same roadmap. Both can be regarded as completed as will be shown in the following.

We have recently demonstrated a streaming workflow in which data from a running PIConGPU simulation is streamed directly to a machine-learning (ML) framework, circumventing the file system bottleneck, see fig. 2. That is, no simulation data is stored on hard drives of the file system. Data is transformed in transit, concurrently to the simulation and the training of the model. The results are published on arXiv, cf. ref. [1], and are accepted for publication in the proceedings of the 39th IEEE International Parallel & Distributed Processing Symposium.

2.4 Runtime tests in a Continuous Integration pipeline

We have expanded our CI infrastructure to include runtime tests, which include both unit tests and integration tests (see PR #4723). These tests are designed to validate the correctness and performance of both the physics algorithms and the computer science

Figure 2: (a-c) Three aspects to streaming between loosely coupled producer and consumer: (a) streaming without going through storage unlocks more bandwidth; (b) reducing simulation data close to the producer lowers bandwidth requirements; (c) to distributed producer and consumer, system topology presents communication paths with vastly different bandwidths which must be reconciled with the loosely-coupled application’s communication requirements. (d) High-level overview of the software stack for data exchange between PIConGPU and the ML framework.

components of the PIConGPU codebase. Currently, unit tests are automatically executed as part of every CI run, ensuring rapid feedback on core functionalities.

However, the integration tests, which are essential for validating full physics simulation workflows, require significantly more resources on a scale that no longer fit standard CI pipelines. We thus currently trigger them manually, even though we already added them to our CI workflows. This constraint limits the frequency and immediacy of integration testing. We noted that with our limited CI resources, running the full integration tests on every CI run was prohibitively expensive in terms of time and resources. It further had the negative impact of slowing down development, since it created a bottleneck in the development workflow by increasing the turnaround time for validating changes.

To address this limitation, we would be happy to work with CASTIEL2 to obtain access to CI runners on EuroHPC resources, since running these tests on a cluster would be much more feasible. This would enable us to incorporate integration tests for large-scale physics simulations directly into the CI pipeline, which would facilitate both the testing and deployment readiness on production EuroHPC systems and also testing the physics to increase code reliability.

As a consequence, we regard the items ‘2. Test suite for continuous integration and code interface for automatization to secure fidelity of physics results in code development’ and ‘3.3. Implement execution of run time tests in continuous integration’ of the roadmap

as final from our side and clear it from the roadmap.

2.5 Python interface for PIConGPU

In the initial deliverable D1.3, we planned to make our prototype of a Python interface PyPIConGPU production ready. This aims to facilitate dissemination and on-boarding of new users in the community but also to enable sophisticated scripted workflows involving, for example, parameter scans, integration into machine-learning workflows and continuous integration and benchmarking on EuroHPC machines. We have made significant progress in this regard – see the 16 merged PRs between 1st December 2024 and 1st June 2025 – and we are in the process of finalizing the last major features. It is planned to switch our internal on-boarding of new users to the Python interface in the next months. Experienced users are already using this in production.

3 Revision of Gap Analysis

No updates compared to previous report. As reported earlier, PIConGPU met the FOM target on OLCF’s Frontier system already and we thus expect similar performance on the JUPITER system at Jülich supercomputing center.

We will make use of the compute time on the European supercomputers, recently acquired within this project, to run (small scale) FOM measurements in order to quantify the impact of recent developments on the FOM. This is reflected by the new item ‘3.8. Perform FOM measurements on European supercomputers’ in the updated roadmap below.

4 Update on Roadmap

We are proceeding along the roadmap. According to our findings we added items 3.6-3.9 to the roadmap, in order to reflect our ongoing work on alpaka3 and the simulation modeling. Apart from that, some items could be cleared, and on some items work has been performed but they can be further worked on, and some items are still open. This is an updated version of the roadmap.

1. Identification of Bottlenecks in the Current Code
 - 1.1. [**► In Progress**] Performance-portability to novel European exascale compute architectures
 - 1.2. [**○ Planned**] I/O capabilities to optimally exploit memory layouts of European exascale systems
 - 1.3. [**✓ Completed**] In-transit data analysis to tackle the data deluge
2. [**✓ Completed with caveats as discussed in 2.4**] Test suite for continuous integration and code interface for automatization to secure fidelity of physics results in code development
3. Next Steps planned

- 3.2. [✓ Completed] Extend and test streaming capability in PIConGPU using openPMD/A-DIOS2 to be used in production
- 3.3. [✓ Completed] Implement execution of run time tests in continuous integration
- 3.4. [○ Planned] Evaluate usefulness of changing input parameter sets of run time tests from native PIConGPU parameter files to PyPIConGPU scripts
- 3.5. [× Not Planned] Develop, test and fine-tune alpaka backend for European exascale compute architectures
- 3.6. [▷ In Progress] Develop, test, and fine-tune new alpaka version, **alpaka3**, in order to better exploit auto-vectorization capabilities of compilers for the European exascale compute architectures.
- 3.7. [▷ In Progress] Identify optimum modeling parameters for simulating stable acceleration beyond 10 GeV in small interaction angle geometries.
- 3.8. [○ Planned] Perform FOM measurements on European supercomputers.
- 3.9. [○ Planned] Apply for compute time for first production runs on a EuroHPC system.

5 Conclusion

As evident from the roadmap, we are making steady progress along the foreseen work plan and have successfully addressed several key challenges. At the same time, new and unforeseen issues have emerged, which have required us to extend and update the original work plan. For a summary, please refer to the Executive Summary.

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